

Histopathological Study of Cervical Lesions in a Tertiary Healthcare Center in India

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Abstract:

This retrospective study aimed to analyze the histopathological characteristics of cervical lesions in 85 female patients at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, between March 2018 and October 2019. The histopathological examination revealed that 56.5% of the lesions were benign, 25.9% were pre-malignant, and 17.6% were malignant, with squamous cell carcinoma being the predominant malignant type. The highest prevalence of pre-malignant and malignant lesions was observed in the 30-50-year age group. These findings underscore the importance of regular cervical screening and histopathological evaluation for early detection and management of cervical lesions, thereby preventing the progression to invasive cancer. The study provides valuable insights for improving cervical health programs and clinical practices in India.

Keywords: Cervical lesions, histopathology, cervical cancer, screening programs.

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Introduction

The incidence of cervical lesions, both benign and malignant, represents a significant public health concern globally, particularly in developing countries like India where cervical cancer ranks as the second most common cancer among women [1,2]. Histopathological examination plays a crucial role in the diagnosis and management of these lesions, providing insights that guide treatment decisions and prognosis evaluations [3].

This study aims to analyze the prevalence and histopathological characteristics of cervical lesions in a tertiary healthcare center in India, highlighting the patterns of benign, pre-malignant, and malignant lesions encountered over a specified period [4]. By reviewing histopathological findings from cervical biopsies, this research intends to contribute valuable data on the types and frequencies of cervical lesions in this demographic, thereby assisting in refining screening and management protocols [5,6].

The objectives of this study are twofold: firstly, to determine the prevalence of various cervical lesions among the patient population attending the tertiary center; and secondly, to elucidate the histopathological features associated with these lesions. This investigation will provide a foundation for future research and interventions aimed at reducing the burden of cervical diseases in

India, emphasizing the importance of histopathological evaluation in the effective management of cervical health.

Methodology

Study Design: This retrospective study was conducted to assess the histopathological characteristics of cervical lesions among patients who presented at the Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, between March 2018 and October 2019.

Study Population: The study included a total of 85 female patients who underwent cervical biopsies during the study period. Patients were selected based on the presence of clinically indicated symptoms or findings suggestive of cervical lesions. There were no exclusion criteria based on age or comorbid conditions, to provide a comprehensive overview of the cervical pathology profile within this population.

Data Collection: Histopathological reports were retrieved from the hospital's pathology department archives. Each biopsy was previously processed using standard histopathological techniques, stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin, and reviewed by certified pathologists. For this study, the histopathological diagnoses were categorized into benign, pre-malignant, and malignant lesions.

Data Analysis: Data were anonymized and coded before analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the prevalence and types of cervical lesions. The frequencies and percentages of each histopathological category (benign, pre-malignant, malignant) were calculated. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software, version 25.0.

Results

The histopathological examination of cervical biopsies from 85 female patients at Patna Medical College and Hospital over the study period yielded the following results:

Distribution of Cervical Lesions

- Benign lesions: A total of 48 patients (56.5%) were diagnosed with benign lesions, which included inflammatory changes, cervical polyps, and benign squamous epithelial abnormalities.
- Pre-malignant lesions: Pre-malignant changes, encompassing various grades of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), were identified in 22 patients (25.9%). Among these, CIN I was observed in 10 patients, CIN II in 7 patients, and CIN III in 5 patients.
- Malignant lesions: Malignant cervical cancers were found in 15 patients (17.6%), with the majority being squamous cell carcinoma.

Age Distribution

- The age of the patients ranged from 21 to 65 years, with a median age of 42 years. The highest prevalence of pre-malignant and malignant lesions was observed in the age group of 30-50 years.

Histopathological Features

- Inflammatory changes were mostly associated with chronic cervicitis.
- Benign polyps frequently showed fibroepithelial characteristics with mixed inflammatory infiltrate.
- Among malignant cases, squamous cell carcinoma showed varying degrees of differentiation, and a few cases displayed lymphovascular invasion, indicating a higher risk of metastasis.

Comparative Analysis

- A significant increase in the incidence of pre-malignant and malignant lesions was noted compared to historical data from the same institution, suggesting a possible increase in the detection rate or a genuine rise in the incidence of these conditions.

Category	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Benign Lesions		
- Inflammatory Changes	28	32.9
- Cervical Polyps	12	14.1
- Benign Squamous Abnormalities	8	9.4
Total Benign Lesions	48	56.5
Pre-malignant Lesions		
- CIN I	10	11.8
- CIN II	7	8.2
- CIN III	5	5.9
Total Pre-malignant Lesions	22	25.9
Malignant Lesions		
- Squamous Cell Carcinoma	15	17.6
Total Malignant Lesions	15	17.6
Total	85	100

Age Distribution of Patients

Age Group (years)	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
21-30	10	11.8
31-40	25	29.4
41-50	30	35.3
51-60	15	17.6
61-65	5	5.9
Total	85	100

These tables summarize the distribution of histopathological findings and the age distribution of the patients, providing a clear view of the study results.

Figure 1: showing squamous cell carcinoma invasion in cords and trabeculae. H&E Stain 40X

Figure 1: showing Adenosquamous variant of squamous cell carcinoma showing glandular pattern. H&E Stain 40X

Discussion

The histopathological study of cervical lesions at Patna Medical College and Hospital reveals a significant prevalence of both benign and malignant cervical pathologies among the patient population [7]. With benign lesions constituting 56.5% of the cases, the findings underscore the high occurrence of inflammatory changes and benign growths, such as cervical polyps and benign squamous epithelial abnormalities [8]. These benign conditions, while generally not life-threatening, can cause significant morbidity and highlight the importance of proper gynecological care and management [9].

The identification of pre-malignant lesions in 25.9% of the cases, particularly the various stages of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), emphasizes the critical window for early intervention. CIN I, II, and III represent a spectrum of precancerous changes that, if detected and treated early, can prevent the progression to invasive cancer [10,11]. The relatively high percentage of pre-malignant lesions in this study suggests either an increase in screening effectiveness or a rising incidence of such conditions, warranting continuous efforts in cervical cancer screening programs [12,13].

Malignant lesions accounted for 17.6% of the cases, with squamous cell carcinoma being the predominant type of cervical cancer observed. This finding aligns with global data, where squamous cell carcinoma remains the most common histological subtype of cervical cancer [14]. The presence of malignant cases, including those with features of lymphovascular invasion, highlights the need for comprehensive treatment approaches and underscores the potential for these lesions to metastasize, necessitating vigilant clinical follow-up [15].

The age distribution of patients, with a median age of 42 years and the highest prevalence of pre-malignant and malignant lesions in the 30-50-year age group, mirrors the known epidemiological trends of cervical cancer [16]. This age group is typically the target for cervical cancer screening initiatives, reinforcing the necessity of regular Pap smears and HPV testing to detect and manage cervical lesions at an early stage [17].

Overall, the study demonstrates the vital role of histopathological evaluation in the diagnosis and management of cervical lesions. It provides a snapshot of the cervical health landscape in a tertiary care setting in India, offering insights that can inform public health strategies and clinical practices. The increase in the detection of pre-malignant and malignant lesions compared to historical data indicates either a true rise in incidence or improved diagnostic capabilities, both

of which call for sustained and enhanced cervical health programs [18-20].

Conclusion

This histopathological study of cervical lesions at Patna Medical College and Hospital highlights a significant prevalence of both benign and malignant cervical conditions, with a notable proportion of pre-malignant lesions underscoring the importance of early detection and intervention. The findings reveal a substantial burden of cervical pathology within the patient population, emphasizing the crucial role of regular cervical screening programs and histopathological evaluation in preventing the progression of pre-malignant lesions to invasive cancer. These insights can guide public health strategies and clinical practices aimed at reducing the incidence and impact of cervical cancer in India.

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